

**PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN OF A
DYSFUNCTIONAL FAMILY**

Tuxtayeva Dilobar Anvarjan qizi

Graduate of the International University of Asia

Annotation: this article provides feedback on the social psychological characteristics of children of an unmarried family about the family and the consequences of their differences in it.

Keywords: family, non-existence, crisis, age periods, conflict, types of conflict.

Movement implemented in our independent state on strengthening the moral, spiritual and spiritual perfection of families are increasing every day. The clear program measures of our government to ensure family strength, expand the possibilities of its social functions, especially to promote the prestige of the family in the upbringing of children and improve the material and domestic conditions of young spouses ensure that family and marriage relations are recognized as values in our country. After all, as the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev said; "the family is a small homeland, the homeland is peaceful if the family is peaceful." The current state of the development of society puts new social tasks of its own before the family. The development of Science and technology, production relations, interaction of people, the circle of relationships are generating emotional emotional changes in the human psyche, and these also influence the character of family life. The description of the family as a value and the study of the role of factors that strengthen it in combination with the education of its prestige in the life of society is an urgent issue, especially the preparation of young people for family life, in which confidence in the future, the formation of feelings of responsibility for the fate of their people and Because Uzbekistan is one of the

countries where official marriages increase from year to year, in which the reduction of marriage deductions becomes more important. This is directly due to the fact that in young people the correct perceptions of family and marriage, life in perspective are formed, they are brought up in the spirit of optimism. Unfortunately, despite the ongoing say'i-efforts, due to the psychological unwillingness of young people to live family life, the lack of clear perceptions of the family's so healthy environment, marital divorces among young families are still being noted. Such a family is called a non-family if there is only one father or mother in the family. When referring to a non-native family, it is worth noting that non-native families occur in different ways. Due to the death of one of the spouses in the family, or due to their divorce, the family may become unstable. Of course, the death of a father or mother in a family is a huge tragedy, but in such families the respect of the soul of the deceased, in relation to him, a positive attitude towards his Shani is preserved. However, "living orphaned" children remain in the dysfunctional families caused by the couple's divorce. "Living orphanhood" has been condemned relatively strongly among the public, especially in children's communities (bo gcha, school, peer circle).

Divorce has a negative effect not only on divorced couples, but also on children living without a father as a result of divorce. In particular, divorce negatively affects the emotions of a girl living without a father, her affection for her mother, the image of a father, which is depicted in a girl, and the psyche of a girl growing up without a father. Often when those who are breaking up are asked the reason for their separation, they try to show some kind of reasons that have become the same for everyone. For example, "our character did not fit", "interference from another person", "rudeness", "material difficulty", "indulgence in drunkenness", "inconvenience of living conditions", "inappropriate parental intervention". It should be noted that the more robust the spiritual climate in the family and the better the couples understand each other these "reasons" cannot be the main cause of the family's crisis. On the contrary, in situations for society-there

is an increase in the number of non-families, inter-family or inter-kin animosity occurs, hatred of one sex towards the Second Sex appears, foxhighabolism increases, an increase in skin-venereal diseases is observed, social activity of the individual decreases. Increased feelings of sleep deprivation in men lead to addiction and addiction to alcohol and various diseases. Increased feelings of malnutrition in women, limited chances of re-marrying, leading to the likes of neuroses, stressors, various hastas, suicide mumkin. Biz in most cases, we give women a child-a child, a household, a soul for the family, for whom we sweat to forgive ourselves, evaluating this feature in them as the most basic-feminine quality. But it is such women who gradually begin to move away from their feminine essence, forget about their personal body egoism, about the fact that they are women. For them, such a way of life is as if satisfied, thereby making them feel happy, but unconsciously this state generates in them the frustrations, a psychic state that arises due to unmet inclinations, creating conditions that cause mental ten immorality, such as something disillusionment, nervousness, sadness. In Uzbek families, one can say innumerable thoughts about the positive manifestations of interaction between father and mother, parents and children, children. Such a relationship, built on the basis of decency, morality, andisha, seems more than enough to form a full-fledged social individuality. All this should have actually been enough for the happiness of the family, for the satisfaction of the family members. But ming unfortunately Khali now shows the high number of divorces, the insufficient finding of families who are not separated but living unhappily, that we do not take into account something here, that we are forgetting something, that we are not paying enough attention to something. In our opinion, what is excluded from this point of view can be the “personal body egoism” of this woman. Failure of a woman's “personal body egoism” to be fully satisfied causes frustration (a psychic condition characterized by the presence of unsatisfied stimulated needs) to occur in her. As a result, a woman develops States of frustration, nervousness, anxiety and frustration with her life. Mother's vaporization directly negatively

affects the personal progress of her child, who is her life expectancy. It is well known that a mother who cannot escape life, who has moved away from her inner essence, who has lost her personal body "egoism", supposedly lives in a "mask" and creates a cover for her child. Due to the limitations of their emotions, such a mother feels a strong need to keep her child in emotional Tobes, and for this purpose creates a specific way of interacting with her child. Such a situation, which plans a long-lasting "infantilism" (braking of the physical and psychic progress of the body), teaches the child the primitive method of dealing with his mother, stops his movement towards the progress in the caretaker and requires the wabola to necessarily fulfill any hidden desires of the mother. To be a good mother, you must first of all be a" woman "and a" happy person". Sacrificing oneself, life, all natural needs to children, family does not mean being a good mother. Such a mother first of all deceives herself, moreover, unconsciously, without her own desire, also thwarts the development of the personality of children. Mental tension in family conditions the incompleteness of the composition of members of the family, the complexity of relationships, incessant employment in women's production, working in state organizations, as well as household cave work, insufficient rest after fatigue are the cause of various body diseases, depression, nervous States, family harmony disorders. In addition, as a result of indifference to the upbringing of children, children who spend most of their time in front of the TV or comp"yuter" are observed to enter the adult world prematurely, as well as cause rapid exhaustion, malaise in pregnant children. Children who are coming of age in a dysfunctional family will come of age without a complete idea of this relationship, as they do not witness the holistic relationship between husband and wife. It is only natural for Yol Ghiz to bring up negative (negative) concepts about his father, who has left in the imagination of a female child, who is raising a child and raising him, especially if this divorce has left feelings. As a fatherless adult boy hears a lot of negative thoughts about men, he hardly believes in the inaccuracy of these concepts. This difficulty, on the other hand, causes an internal

struggle to arise in it. In a son who is much pampered by his mother, or who in society mainly believes that women are masters, an attitude of indifference, infertility arises towards men. In many cases, the desire to help the mother of the young girl in the boy prompts her to give up free life. As a result of the fact that many boys remain in front of their mothers, the exposure to the opposite sex will subside, or vice versa, there are cases of turning against the mother and leaving the House, obscuring the mother, the woman. As the feeling of guilt increases, rude treatment of women is formed in such children, or, on the contrary, it occurs to live subordinate to them for the rest of their lives. In addition, it is also observed that in a dysfunctional family, an end to the position of the son is imposed by the mother on the eldest son in the role of the father. In most cases, single mothers involuntarily give their young sons a mahnavi taizik, yah" I see from you that I have not seen from your father", "if you grow up, you will make it to me, you will take such a thing", losing the unobtrusive humility inherent in the child's youth and downloading to him the masculinity of an older man.

A girl who is coming of age in a dysfunctional family can also take a wrong approach to the relationship between a woman and a man. It is observed that his personal sexual identification is volatile, that yah he is obedient in life and agrees to everything, that he does not demand anything, or, on the contrary, that he is independent of everything and demands freedom. An example of this is the process of emancipation (striving for freedom), which is currently developing. Yahni, yol Ghiz may also not persuade a man to prevail or to solve problems by a man after marriage, a girl who has grown up in a family that demonstrates agility, resourcefulness, entrepreneurship in raising a child and takes all the problems in the family on her shoulders. However, a woman-mother does not create a negative understanding in children if she treats men correctly. A woman has the opportunity to form a positive attitude in her children towards men she knows, whom she respects. They can be a woman's father, brothers, acquaintances.

One of the requirements for children by family members, harmony in mutual

responsibility and influence is an important source of comprehensive development of the personality of the child. The family in which the child lives and is brought up is a natural resource for him, which leaves a special mark on the character and behavior of the child. The personality of the child is formed in many ways and, mainly, in the family. Learns the elementary rule of living. The educational effect of the family will be so strong that in our eyes the characteristics of the parents' characters will seem to pass to the child in a biological way. Therefore, it is not for nothing that Hamailani is called the "school of emotions". Household living conditions in the Family, Family Foundation, values, relationships of family members, their behavior, moral qualities, needs and interests begin to influence the child from the very beginning of his youth. The spiritual image of the father and mother in particular, the sociifatsifelgusidat determines before what kind of character traits are formed in the child. Because the child first imitates those who are close to him, they begin to express their desire in himself. In addition to exemplary families in the upbringing of children, it is also possible to meet unobtrusive families who are limited in the knowledge of creating materiality for children, who do not think about the upbringing of the child, about his future, who do not pay attention. The divorce of family members or the death of one of the father and mother, non-families arise in the relationship.

The fact that one of the family members does not participate in the upbringing of a child creates a number of objective difficulties. As a result, it is the responsibility of the mother who is engaged in the upbringing of the child to have two difficult tasks: to financially support the children left behind and to be responsible for their upbringing. In addition, a single mother begins to feel a huge mental challenge as well as great responsibility for the upbringing of children. A characteristic feature of a nonlinear family is its uniqueness (closeness). Tevarak-it will be somewhat more difficult to influence it from the environment. Because family members mother and children are characterized by their inferiority, inferiority and reluctance towards full family members. The presence of a specific

mental environment in a dysfunctional family and its occasional changes have a special effect on the mental, moral and mental maturation of the child being brought up in this family. For example, a child's calm and free attitude to his parents positively affects his social consciousness, behavior, increased self-confidence. It is known that a child raised in a full family is usually less worried about family and family members, there will be a feeling of harmony about his own family. Non-stop family conflicts and countless conflicts that occur due to the separation of the family, the frequent discussion of family problems loses the child's tranquility, warmth, peace, peace of mind, causes an increase in self-doubt. As a result of observations, it turned out that the concept of how young a child can not imagine the family and its consequences, separation, is incorrect. Children suffer severe anguish from family conflict and divorce, no matter what age they are, remain mentally depressed, human. For no reason, family conflicts leave an unpleasant mark on the child's imagination in his memory, which negatively affects his mentally normal development. As a result, children of such a family awaken a feeling of fear, a feeling of hadixirash, and even defects in children's speech begin to appear, stutter and become insecure. Although preschool children initially express a very sluggish, imperceptible relationship to family separation, gradually in older preschool years they begin to feel more deeply without a father or motherhood. Children's feelings of paternity can be observed in their various behaviors, including changes in their attitudes towards their mother. Children's strong interests in tevarak-surrounding reality begin to subside, their attitude towards peers and adults changes dramatically, becoming capricious, quarrelsome, talkative and not listening to adults. The most dangerous thing is that sincerity in the child begins to gradually take the place of disdain, indifference, because the child sees the process of family separation, the coldness of his closest people towards each other, bereavement relationships firsthand, is angry and, finally, is used to it. The one-sided conduct of upbringing in the family, insufficient attention to the personal nature of the child, that is, the absence of equal influence from the

father and mother, the qualitative aspect of the relationship with the child, which has gradually changed-slowly in it, the feeling of lying down towards his father or mother causes a sensation, which puts him at great risk for his development. The social understanding of the child will be somewhat narrower than the understanding of the child in a full family, since the performance of the mother in the family as both mother and father does not expand her social imagination. The narrowness of concepts about social life for children brought up in a dysfunctional family Boys, which is clearly noticeable in young girls, because the interest of boys in sports plays that they interact in games, labor activities, ensures a certain level of growth of social concepts in them. In the case of a girl, the opposite is true, since they spend the main part of their life in communication between mothers, a situation that presents some difficulties in her understanding of the path of her future life. In my opinion, the following are the reasons why the number of non-families increases day by day. One of the main reasons for this is the fact that our young people do not have a full - fledged and psychologically correctly literate picture of family life. Most young people imagine a family chayote as a "honeymoon", although family life is a test of great fate for every age. Each family undergoes a different economic, moral, individual-psychological, including endurance testing. Unfortunately, a certain number of young families could not withstand these tests, and a sharp increase in the number of non-families began to increase. In conclusion, I can say that we do not interfere rudely in the personal life of families, and at the same time, we are ahead of the trials and challenges that are inevitable for young people to meet in the family life, considering it not negatively affecting the fullness of the family, the health of family members, I think we should help.

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